

American Psychological Association, (APA) Style & Referencing: A Brief Study

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Abstract:- In an academic writings and scientific research different methods of in- text citation and referencing are used for making writings more authentic and formal. American Psychological Association (APA), the Modern Language Association (MLA), Chicago/Turabian style are Used in Business, History and the fine Arts etc. But in social sciences research APA method of in- text citation and referencing is used. In this article the researcher has given various examples of in-text citation and referencing using desk work method of collecting information to give basic ideas on using APA methods while writing research articles, Thesis/dissertation and research reports. Being based on the objective of this article this article has highly focused on basic ideas regarding use of APA style in research work.

Keywords:- American Psychological Association, Referencing, In-text Citation, Research article, Thesis/dissertation and Academic Writings.

Objective: To assess the APA methods referencing and in-text citation style based on APA 6th and 7th edition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Research work and an academic writing without citation and referencing are not taken as more reliable. That's why research task is incomplete without its results are generalized with the concerned community. Although such sharing is accomplished in a different ways both formal and informal, the traditional medium for communicating research results is the scientific and academic writings i.e., journals. It is repository of accumulated knowledge of a field. The findings and analysis, the successes and failures, and the perspectives of many investigators over many years are recorded in the literature. Being close with the literatures (through review of literatures) allows the researcher to go on the right path to contribute something new in the concerned field.

It (APA format) is an official style of the American psychological Association (APA) and is generally used to cite sources in various disciplines i.e., political science, sociology, anthropology, history, geography, psychology, education, and the other disciplines. While knowing about history of the APA style, it is originated in the article published in psychological Bulletin that published (1929) the basic guidelines for academic writings and scientific research. These basic guidelines are virtually expanded into APA method of publication to make academic writings and research work reliable and plagiarism free.

II. METHODS OF STUDY

For conducting this research the desk work method is used mostly, web based information have been gained and presented it in a particular format. This article is absolutely based on secondary method of data collection and descriptive methods of data analysis.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Researchers and student's writing about social events and phenomenon under APA style are able to transform knowledge, ideas and any sort of findings in a consistent format. It helps to pacify readers thirst to know what to look in a research articles and academic writings published in journals and other forms of writings. That's why this article is meaningful to all the authors to know APA referencing and citation style of uniformity and consistency in their writing.

IV. FINDINGS

Throughout the paper, any potential researcher needs to follow APA format guidelines given below:-

Basic Tips
1) While following APA style of writings, page margins should be one inch on all sides of the A4 size paper
2) Text materials should be typed using double- space
3) Headings also should be typed with double- space
4) 0.5 inches indent in the first line of every paragraph.
5) Use an accessible font e.g., Times New roman 12 pt, Arial 11pt. or Georigic 11 pt. and others
6) Indent page number on every page on the top right corner.

V. APA STYLE WHILE WRITING ARTICLE FOR JOURNAL

A. Writing Abstract

It is a summary of research and academic writings that follows title page. As per APA format, it should not exceed more than 100 to 200 words. But it can vary with the specific publication, journal or instructor requirements.

An abstract is expressed in one paragraph of 100 to 200 words. It is the expressions of entire paper in an instructed sequence that includes: objectives the overall study, the research problems, methods, hypothesis, limitations, significance of the study as identified by researcher; the basic blueprint or designing of the study and the core findings as well as the result of the study. In a dissertation or thesis the abstract is expressed in a separate page, after the title page and acknowledgements but before the table of contents (Mc Combes, 2019, and February 28).

B. Writing Main Body

The core part of the writings includes actual contributions of the author. In a research paper / article / report, the main body will be divided into further section i.e., *introduction, methods, result, and discussion section.*

C. Ways to Arrange References

This part of the article includes a systematic presentation of all the sources that is followed by the researcher while writing the respective paper. If the researcher has borrowed any sort of information in any part of the writing, it needs to be addressed properly in this section. Over handy paper, it needs to be properly referenced in this section. It helps to the author to be safe from possible unnecessary charge of plagiarism and intellectual cheating.

VI. APA STYLE IN AN OTHER ACADEMIC WRITINGS

A. In-text citation

While writing an academic writings, it is obligatory to include citations in the text addressing where did the writer find the information used. Such processes are called in-text citations and APA format suggests that citing in APA format in the text of research paper, the researcher should use author's name followed by the date of publication (Cherry, 2020, August 25). For example :- (**Sharma, 2010, P. 25**)

Important Tips for Reference pages

- New page for References.
- Write the term "References" at the centre top of the paper.
- Put all references in alphabetic order.
- Align the first line of a reference flush with the left margin.
- Indent each additional line (actually accomplished by using the TAB Key).
- Make sure the reference section in double-spaced.
- Use *italic* for title of books, Journal, Magazines, and newspapers. (Source: Streefkerk, Raimo. (2020, November 6.)
- In this section, all sources cited should include.

While including in-text citation in an academic writings and research work, it must be correctly addressed within in-text citation immediately following the quote. Direct quotations must be reproduced as the original (exactly), including cording, spelling, capitalization, and punctuation and other signs. For instance: -**Sharma and Shrestha (2004)** opined that "One clear result of representations focused on the empowerment process of women in developing society"(P.112).

The editing note [**Sic.**] is used if the quotation contains a mistake (grammatical or otherwise); indicate this error as original source by using after the error, including the square brackets.

a) Long Direct – quotations

Citation longer than 40 words should be indented and double spaced with no quotation marks. For long quotations, the Punctuation is placed before the parentheses. For instance:

Sharma and Shrestha (2004) explain this view:
The situation of back warded
.....
.....
..... No matter (P.103)

b) Short direct quotations

In an academic writings quotations shorter than 40 words should be placed into a text and enclosed by double quotations marks (" ").

c) Quotes within quotations

Occasionally, a quote will have within it a quote from second source. In this case, for long quotations, enclose direct quotation in double quotation mark, and for short quotations, use single quotations mark to enclose Quotes,

Example (Short)
Sharma and Shrestha (2004) note that "
..... replaced it after that correctly"
(P.152).

Example (Long)
Sharma and Shrestha (2004) note that "
.....
.....
.....(p.340)

In any academic writing indirect quotes and paraphrased ideas are allowed to be placed without using the original wording. These ideas or arguments became combined with the researcher's agreements, but they must be cited appropriately. For instance:- **Sharma and Shrestha (2004)** supports this idea (P.112).

Sample of Narrative in-text citation and a Parenthetical citation

This is a narrative in-text citation. The author's name is in the text of the sentence. The page number (p. 42) is at the end of the sentence.

Stein (2018) studied whether the early onset of Alzheimer’s disease affected individuals younger than 30. His findings revealed that individuals as young as 20 were affected by the disease (p. 42). Another study found similar data, showing that individuals as young as 18 displayed symptoms of the disease (Tang & Pierce, 2014, p. 231). Even though both studies involved individuals in different hemispheres, the results were similar.

This is a parenthetical citation. In parentheses are the last names of authors, year published and page number.

These are the references for the in-text citations in the project. These references, are listed on the final page, and contain the full information about each source.

Source: <https://www.citationmachine.net/apa>, accessed on 31 October, 2021

d) More about In-text citations

In any research work and in an academic writings, it is highly recommended to show the sources of information obtained from its original sources i.e., books, journals, magazines, newspapers, electronic and web sources. While applying these quotations it must be referred as prescribed by APA method both in the text and in the reference list.

While following APA style in an academic writings and research work, each and every sentence containing ideas or information of others must include in a reference containing the author's name, the date of publication, and the page or chapter reference, if applicable. Page references are typically only required in direct citations and are needed for indirect citations when drawing on an obscure element of an author's argument, or a point with which is dealt only briefly. If an author's name is mentioned in a sentence, it must include the date and page reference (If applicable). In parentheses after the author's last name, if an author is not mentioned in the sentence, include the author's last name date of publication, and page reference in parentheses at the end of the sentence.

Example:-

Timalsina (2072 BS), Quote (p. 67).
 Or
 quote (Timalsina, 2072 BS, P. 67)

If citing sources, within a paragraph, more than one, include both the author's name and year of publication in the first citation, but, the year can be omitted in subsequent citations.

However, if the source can be confused with another one i.e., describing two articles by the same author in the same paragraph then include the year in all citations.

For example:-

(Timalsina, 2020: Upreti 2018)

- a. If no pages are in the document
 If there are no page number (e.g.) electronic documents).use the paragraph number as "Para 1, 2, 3..."

Cite the heading and the paragraph number if paragraph number is not visible (e.g., Timalsina, 2020, Nepal – India, Para, 4).

- b. Books/Reports Published by organization
 In course of applying citation, if the sources are of any organization or groups, if should be addressed as: - (e.g., United Nations),

- c. Works with no author
 If no author's name is used in any text, the first few words of the title of the work in place of the author should include. In this course use double quotation marks around the title of an article or chapter, and use italics for the title of a periodical, book, brochure, or report and so on. For instance:-

"Indian micro-management" (2015)
 defines

d. Anonymous author (Unknown / impersonal)

If a work is designated as "Anonymous" write the word **anonymous** in place of the author.

For example:

Anonymous, (2020)

e. Class notes, interviews, personal communication

In course of citing personal communications in any academic writings and research work including letters, emails, personal interview, phone conversations, and similar sources that contain incommunicable data (e.g. class note) that are not included in the reference list, but need to be cited in-text. To cite personal communications, include the initials and last name of the communication and that exact data.

Example:-

SarojTimalsina (Personal) Communication, April 14, 2020) (SarojTimalsina, P.C. 11)

B. Ellipsis

In course of academic writings if unnecessary part of a paragraph is to be avoided the writer can follow an ellipsis that helps to omit words or sentences that is not important in the text being written.

For example, from a direct quotation, indicate this by using through spaced periods in place of the missing words (.....). But if it happens at the end of a sentence, use for periods. Be careful that, all commas and periods must be within the quotation marks. Keep in mind that the quote must still embody the original idea and the author fairly represented.

For Example: Sharma & Shrestha (2004) have asserted that "....." (P. 130).

C. Tables

While writing a research paper table are generally expressed. It provides an effective ways of expressing a large number of data on a required amount of space. Tables should be used to express vital data directly related to the content of the paper and to simplify text that would otherwise be dense with numbers. If the writer includes a table repeating the same information in the text is worthless. The following information should contain with table

- Table number – Number all tables not text.
 - Title – Explanatory title.
 - Headings – each column should contain a short heading text
 - Do not refer "the table above" term but use table1, 2,3...).
- While doing analysis.

a. Sample Table:-

Stubhead	df	F	η	p
Row 1	1	0.67	.55	.41
Row 2	2	0.02	.01	.39
Row 3	3	0.15	.33	.34
Row 4	4	1.00	.76	.54

Note. This is where authors provide extra information important to the data, such as findings that approach statistical significance depending on the p value: Significant at the p<0.05 level.

(Source:

<https://www.google.com/search?q=sample+table+in+apa+style+writing>)

Table 1.

The Number of thousands of litres of hot sauce consumed in Canada, the United States, and Britain 2007-2012

Column1	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Canada	12	18	13	22	19	18
United States	57	64	66	72	74	69
Britain	20	16	15	18	21	19
Total Litres	89	98	94	112	114	106

Note. Data for hot sauce consumption in the United States from Kantar Media (2010), for Canada from Statistics Canada (2011), and for Britain from Euromonitor International (2010b).

(Source: <https://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl>)

b. Sample Figures:-

In the figure the font size for all parts should be between 8 and 14

- Include a legend to explain any symbols used in the table
- Use descriptive caption but short

Figure 1

Sample Figure Title

Note. A note describing content in the figure would appear here.

Source: <https://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl>

To cite figure, refer by number (Figure – 1)

Labeled Elements of a Figure in APA Format

Source: <https://www.bibliography.com/apa/using-apa-figures-correctly/>

Figure 1. Division of Business Expenses. From Patel, 2019, p. 7.

Note: If the figure you are using is just for decoration, use this template without the figure label.

Source: <https://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl>

D. Avoid plagiarism:

Plagiarism involves taking someone else's ideas or arguments, putting them into your own words, without proper citation. To avoid plagiarism, cite all sources, information used in the text that requires quotations and both in-text and reference list citations. If using another's ideas, into your own words, it does not need quotation marks, but in text and reference list citation is must.

Saint Mary's university (2009), Plagiarism is the presentation of words, ideas or techniques of original another as one's won. It is lawful if it is obtained following prescribed methods by APA, MLA & other styles with proper citation. It is not illegal and unethical if it is used as per prescribed manner by APA, MLA and other methods of citations as well as referencing.

A common knowledge does not require citation. For instance USSR collapsed on 1989. But UN was established in 1945 AD and its members have reached 193 by the end of 2020 A.D. (Brooks, 2020, P.80).

E. Referencing

In social sciences, APA format of citations in an annotated bibliography, and add a synopsis for each entry. The synopsis is found immediately after the citation, and it should be indented on the left hand margin the entire bibliography should be double spaced. Further about referencing,

• Journal Articles a) Journal Article with DOI
Ex-Timalsina, Saroj (2012). "Neapl-India Relations"*Aanusheelan A multi disciplinary journal*, 10130L.

• Journal Articles a) Journal Article without DOI (electronic)
Ex- Timalsina Saroj (2012).Nepal – India Relations.*Aanusheelan, A multi disciplinary Journal Vol. Page* Retrieved from ttp/www.timelsc.com/

b) Journal Article with DOI (Print articles)

Ex- Timalsina, Saroj (2012) "Nepal and India Relations.*Aanusheelan a multi disciplinary Journal 9. 15-18.*)

a) Journal article with more than seven authors

To reference a journal article with more than seven authors, list the first six followed by an ellipsis, then the last anther. For instance:- Sharma, R, Bhattari, S., Gyawalai, P, Ghimire, S, Timalsina, SK, Subedi, S Pokherel, K.)

b) Chapter in an edited book

Timalsina, S. (2012). "Nepal – India Relations" in Ram K. Dahal (Ed.), *Diplomatic Relation of Nepal* (PP. 110-115) Kathmandu: M.K Publications.

c) Use of encyclopedia

"Right against exile". (2015). *An Encyclopedia of Britannia* (Vol. 10, P. 105). Balshih. D. Waltz.

d) Magazine article

Dahal, R.K. (2010, April 10). "Article title". *Magazine*, name Italic, 205, 3.

e) Newspaper article

Sharma, K. (2020, April, 10). 'Title of Article', *The Kathmandu Post*, 6.

f) Government Document

Ministry of Health (2010) Kathmandu.

g) Unpublished conference paper

Sharma, K. (2006, May). Title of article paper presented at the annual convention of the international Studies Association, Kathmandu.

h) Grey Literature. (Brouchures, etc)

Sharma, K. (N.D).Politics at University (Brochure) Author.

i) Film and documentaries
Sharma, K. (Proucer), &Bhattari, K. (Director). (1998). *Amakamaya* (Feature Film). Kathmandu: Digital pictures.

j) Video Clip
University of California, Mathau. (2010). Political discourse (Video fire). Retrieved from <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v:3D9D98Vsxnr>.

k) Lecture's notes
Timalsina, S.K. (2020, November). Political Participation. Power point preservation at Bachelor Degree's first year guest lecture's class. Bhaktapur. Retrieved from <http://.....2020/..... pdf>.

l) Citing multiple works in one parenthesis if, it should follow the below given style:-
If the given works are done by the same author, the journal is stated once followed by the dates in order chronologically.

Example:-Sharma (2010, 2012, 2013).

If these works are by multiple authors than the reference, are ordered alphabetically by the first author separated by a semicolon as follows: (Sharma and Bhattari, 2012; Bhattari &Dahal, 2015).

m) Citing a secondary source
In this situation the original author and date should be started first followed by as cited in following by author and date of the secondary source.

For example:-Sharma and Bhattari (2012) as cited in Sharma, Bhattari &Dahal, 2015 (<https://www.medoley.com/guides/apa-atetion-guide>).

APA Referencing style updated to 7thEdition!

Guidelines modified to make updates to the APA referencing style published in the 7th edition of the publication Manual of the American Psychological Association (2020) should be followed by the author who is going to write new writings. While researcher and authors and students who have already commenced thesis or other major works should continue to use APA 6th edition.

There are both significant and minor changes in the new edition. They are:-

F. Significant Changes:

a) Multiple authors –
Applying in-text citations for three or more authors it should include the name of the first author only followed by et.al.

b) Reference-
While following APA 7th amendment, it should include all authors' names and the list entries for work done by these authors.

c) For work done by more than by 20 authors-

For work done by more than *twenty* authors, it should include the name of the first 19 authors followed by on ellipsis (.....) and then the final author's name.

d) Publication:-
Place of publications is no longer included in reference as per the 7th amendment.

e) Issue number-
Journals that have an issue number should include the issue number in parentheses immediately after the volume number.

f) DOI-In this format: <https://doi.org/xxxxx> DOIs are not required.

g) Retrieved-It is not necessary to include the word "retrieved from" before a URL.

h) Database names and URLs
In an academic writings and research work databases items should not be included in references, except for databases such a chorine, FRIC and Factiva that include works of limited circulation for these items include the name of the database and the URL for the specific work.

VII. FOR ELECTRONIC WORKS

The reference should be the same as in printed version of the electronic works that do not have DOI or a directly linked URL (<https://libguides.murdoch.edu.and/APA>).

A. Writing a conclusion

A conclusion is an important part of the paper. It provides easy way to grab the theme of the articles or academic writings to the reader. It should be presented in a single paragraph and suggest possible future research on the topic. While reminding the reader of the contents and importance of the paper it accomplishes this by stepping back from the specifics in order to view the bigger picture of the document.

An Easy check list for writing a conclusion

- Is it the theme of the paper accurately restated here?
 - Are the main points of the paper addressed and pulled together?
 - Do you remind the reader of the importance of the topic?
 - Make sure that the paper places its findings in the context of real source change.
 - It there a sense of closure?
 - The paper should naturally come to an ends not to leave the leader hanging
 - Do you avoid presenting new information?
 - No new ideas should be introduced in the conclusion.] is simply a review of the material that is already present in the paper. The only new idea would be th suggesting of a direction for future research. (WALDE UNIVERSITY. (n.d). Writing paper. Conclusions: Retrieved for <https://academic guide: Wolden.edu/writing centre/writing process/conclusion.>)
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VIII. CONCLUSION

APA is the style of the formal documentation of sources used by the researcher while doing research work or in an academic writings. This form of writings are used by researcher in research papers concerning the social sciences, like political science, geography, economics, Sociology, Public administration, Culture history, anthropology as well as educations and other fields. When working with APA there are two things to keep in mind; intent citations and the reference page. Intent citations will use the author's name and the data within your research paper. These citations will refer back to the reference page at the end, which lists all the sources that the author has used in his/her research paper. This article has focused on the use of resource authentically while writing academic writings such as articles/thesis/dissertation or any research papers.

IX. FURTHER RESEARCH POTENTIALS

For further up new or latest changes can be studied by new researcher in the field.

REFERENCES

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